

IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Through the use of modern information technologies in education, the development of effective approaches, the introduction of advanced methods of education, the growing young generation will be closely acquainted with the achievements of world civilization, the fundamental improvement of the system of training potential specialists, and the wide range of information resources of the world. ensuring their widespread use is one of today's urgent issues. This article talks about the importance of innovative educational technologies in today's advanced educational environment. Information was given on ways to make education more effective, how to use modern technologies during the lesson.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, innovative education, innovation, pedagogical technology, information technology, traditional education.*

Today, in our country, an educational system aimed at integration into the new world information-educational environment is being established. This is followed by significant changes in the organization of the educational process that respond to modern technical capabilities. The introduction of modern information technologies into the field of education makes it possible to qualitatively facilitate and change the methods of education and the forms of organization of the teaching process based on a new approach. Information and communication technologies are the most important part of the process of modernization of the educational system. ICT is information processing methods with various technical and software devices. It is primarily computers with the necessary software and telecommunications equipment on which data is stored.

The modern world level of development of information and communication technologies is such that the creation of a national system compatible with the integration of the infrastructures of the world information space and the national information and computing network in the republic is an important factor in the effectiveness of the national economy, management, science and education. These problems are very complex and at the same time urgent for our republic. The results of the implementation of economic, structural and other changes that are currently being carried out depend on how and in what time frame the problems related to informatization are solved in the republic.

Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education If in the school, students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and education of a person, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure. Therefore, modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies have a great role in training

qualified professionals in higher educational institutions and faculties. Knowledge, experience and interactive methods of pedagogic technology and pedagogic skills ensure that pupils-students have an educated, mature qualification.

Modern educational development has brought a new direction - innovative activity to the field. By the 21st century, which is considered to be the age of information - highly developed technologies, the attention to the issue of wide introduction of innovation in the educational process has increased. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, innovation has entered the education system as one of the first compared to other fields, and we can see how innovation is reflected in the educational process. The entry of innovation into the system of pedagogical sciences was determined by the following. a) Gender pedagogy; b) Heuristic pedagogy; c) Compulsory pedagogy; g) Androgogic pedagogy - we can see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation into teaching methods. If the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of students in the course of the lesson, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding. The interactive method is understood as active action together (teacher and student, student and student). We can see the introduction of innovation into the form of lessons in the example of standard, non-standard and virtual lesson forms. There are types of innovation in teaching types: problem-based learning, heuristic learning, graded learning, integrated learning, interactive learning, informal learning, formal learning, non-formal learning. Multimedia, electronic boards and other tools can be used as an example of innovation in teaching tools. We can see innovation in teaching methods in the following methods.

1. Active method - encourages students to be active during the lesson, to think and reflect on a certain situation and reality.

2. Passive method - leads to the formation of a one-sided understanding of the studied subject in students during the lesson.

3. Interactive method. The purpose of this method is based on the joint active behavior of the teacher and students during the lesson.

We can see the innovation of the lesson in the following form.

- a) Standard lesson - the structure of the lesson does not change.
- b) Non-standard lesson - the structure within the lesson changes.
- c) Virtual lesson - i.e., distance learning.

The concept of "new" occupies a central place in pedagogical innovation. It also arouses interest in special, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogical science. According to V.A. Slastenin, the private news is current modernization involves updating one of the elements of a specific system product. Conditional innovation is a combination of certain elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation. Innovation is a tool: a new method, methodology, technology, etc. V.I. Zagvyazinsky defined the new concept and said that the new in pedagogy is not just an idea, but approaches, methods, and technologies that have not yet been used, but the elements of the pedagogical process are combined or taken separately, and effectively fulfill the tasks of education and upbringing in changing conditions and situations. represents the advanced beginnings of the solution. Pedagogical innovation is the process of developing, implementing, testing and evaluating innovations in the field of education that help to effectively achieve these goals. Among them: the educational process changes over time, the labor market makes new demands on future employees, and teaching is changed, adapted to new goals, new pedagogical methods, methods and methods are needed to achieve this. Innovations in education help to

achieve the following goals: Humanization, democratization of the educational process; Activation of students' cognitive activity; Improving the effectiveness of the organization of education and training; Changes of educational material from the point of view of methodology and didactics. An approach to education is a set of basic principles, requirements, and goals that form the basis for new technologies.

The requirement of modern education is not to give students as much knowledge as possible, but to teach them to learn on their own, not only to know, but also to be able to work with the received information. Pedagogical innovations are based on two main approaches: The student-centered approach involves directing the educational process to each student. Modern pedagogy should take into account the unique experience and character of each student, develop his individuality and talent. Implementation of this approach involves relying on the principles of choice (students can choose the fields they want), trust (by teachers lack of authoritarian pressure), creativity and success, subjectivity, individuality.

In conclusion, the use of these innovative technologies is used in the teaching process at the Afghan National Education Center, and Afghan students are also able to gain deep knowledge, create new ideas, think freely, and expand their vocabulary. are achieving effective results in increasing their scientific potential.

REFERENCES

1. 1. Information and communication technologies and systems. Textbook. Dadabaeva R.A., Nasridinova Sh.T., Shoakhmedova N.Kh., Ibragimova L.T., Ermatov Sh.T., "Sano-standart", 2017.-552b.
2. Information and communication technologies and systems. Textbook. Kenjabayev A.T., Ikramov M.M., Allanazarov A.Sh., Publishing house of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan. 2017-408b.
3. Taylakov N.I. Prospects of implementation of modern information technologies in the educational system // Education and training -T 2002
4. Akhmedova, M. M., & Khomidova, M. M. K. (2021). Modern methods and technologies in teaching literature. *Scientific progress*, 2(3), 317-325.
5. Rustambekov M.M. Use of modern information technologies in the educational system of schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan. M.: Trends in the development of higher education in new conditions, 2021.